
Our world is becoming dependent on cyber-physical systems (CPS) providing unprecedented innovation opportunities but also representing unprecedented complexity. We need to design future CPS to make sure that they become human-centred and part of a circular economy.

Cyber-physical systems have far-reaching implications

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Cyber-physical systems (CPS) integrate computation, communication and physical processes to form small- as well as large-scale systems with improved or new capabilities. The term cyber lends itself to some confusion since it can be seen as either stemming from “kubernetes” – referring to feedback systems – or relating to the use of computers or computer networks. Both interpretations generally make sense for CPS, of which there are many types!

CPS have been available since at least the 1970s with the advent of direct digital control and are thus not new. Integrating and leveraging advances in a combination of technologies (e.g. materials, batteries, sensors, machine learning, processing and communications) is, however, providing entirely new capabilities, enabling the creation of new types of systems. These trends are well illustrated by automated vehicles as CPS. However, the trends and the example only touch upon part of the societal impact that future CPS are likely to have. CPS are applicable in – and across – all domains. They are, moreover, increasingly collaborative, connected over their lifecycles and deployed in open society scale settings (“robots at home and on the streets”).

With our societies increasingly dependent on well-functioning CPS (water, energy, transport, health, manufacturing, etc.), it becomes crucial that we develop such CPS to be human-centred; that is, CPS that are explicitly supporting interactions and collaborations with humans, and help us in addressing sustainability challenges. This requires us to be able to balance and manage the complexity of future CPS. This article elaborates on these perspectives.

Key insights

- CPS provide unprecedented innovation opportunities through the synergetic integration of cyber components (software, data-driven algorithms, computation and communications) with physical components, equipping CPS with a unique and evolving set of capabilities.
- Humans constitute a key aspect in CPS design, with manifold interactions between humans and CPS not receiving sufficient attention. These interactions, as well as the capabilities and limitations of both CPS and humans, need to be considered in conjunction in order to improve usability and manage risks; the automation paradox is more relevant than ever.
- Future CPS will represent unprecedented complexity, which has to be balanced and made manageable. This calls for new scientific theories, lifecycle engineering methodologies, curriculum renewal and lifelong learning. Collaborating CPS form cyber-physical systems of systems (CPSoS) where interactions, operational management and emergence require specific attention.
- The increasing penetration of CPS represents an ongoing socio-technical shift that requires industrial and societal transformation to adapt organizations, processes, standards, legislation and more, highlighting the need for testbeds and involvement of a multitude of stakeholders.

Key recommendations

- Promote organizations and schemes, such as competence networks, to raise awareness and drive the collaboration and change required to obtain circular and human-centred CPSoS
- Undertake R&D efforts into methodologies for:
 - Human-centred CPS, taking into account CPS complexity and the importance and potential of designing CPS and their supporting development environments to appropriately interact with and support humans.
 - Circular CPS and CPS to support the transition to a circular economy, emphasizing needs for cross-fertilization between CPS and sustainability collaborative research.

What do we mean by CPS?

The concept of cyber-physical systems (CPS), as coined in the US in 2006, has had significant impact. It led among other things to the introduction of a new foundational and multidisciplinary research programme by the US National Science Foundation and to the launching of Industry 4.0 in Germany in 2010. In Europe there has also been growing interest and awareness including through a number of roadmapping efforts [1]. At the same time, it is clear that some confusion remains as to the meaning of CPS and that several domains are often using other terms to represent similar types of systems. To illustrate the slight confusion of terminology, consider the following question posed at the HiPEAC ACACES summer school in July 2020:

Which interpretation of a cyber-physical system (CPS) – what it is or represents, makes sense to you?

1. CPS is really the same thing as embedded systems
2. CPS is the same as Industry 4.0 (I4.0)
3. CPS represent feedback systems
4. CPS represents integrations of computation, networking and physical processes
5. CPS is an umbrella term covering e.g. I4.0, IoT and Industrial IoT
6. CPS is a clever term invented to gain more research funding

The summer school participants provided a plethora of answers, covering all possibilities. This response was not unexpected, given the potential dual interpretation of the term “cyber”:

- *cyber* – the use of computers or computer networks – with many connotations such as cyberspace and cybersecurity [16].
- *cyber* – as part of the concept of cybernetics, coined by Norbert Wiener in the 1940s, from the Greek word “kubernetes” – “governance”, referring to feedback systems [2].

The initial definition of CPS, as the “integration of computation, networking and physical processes where CPS range from miniscule (e.g. pacemakers) to large-scale (e.g. national power grids)”, has the characteristic of being very general. In fact, as suggested by Alberto Sangiovanni-Vicentelli during the EU-funded CyPhERS project: which system will not be of a CPS nature in the future? In CyPhERS [17], we set out to provide an agenda for CPS research. One conclusion was that we needed a taxonomy, a way to characterize CPS to describe different types of CPS [3]. In the late 1970s, Enslow wanted to clarify the concept of “distributed processing”, and introduced dimensions for characterizing them [18]. He had a strong opinion on what constituted a distributed system along these dimensions. In the CyPhERS approach,

however, we decided to recognize that there are many different types of CPS that are distinguishable through a number of characteristics, such as relating to the technological emphasis at hand, the scale and the level of automation. Agreeing on terminology is not always easy. It is interesting to note that even some of the most experienced *systems engineers* had problems on agreeing on a definition of “systems”. The Greek word “systema” refers to “a set of things working together as parts of a mechanism or an interconnecting network; a complex whole”, or “a set of principles or procedures according to which something is done” [19]. However, they were able to reach a consensus on what characterizes systems [20]. This speaks further in favour of characterizations as a tool to improve communication.

Figure 1. Terms mirroring an expanding technological shift (with an emphasis on the cyber side)

A further source of confusion may stem from the plethora of terms as illustrated in Figure 1.

In the author’s view, these terms reflect different perspectives to similar technological trends. For example, Industry 4.0 represents a manufacturing (and thus domain-specific) specific interpretation of CPS, while IoT emphasizes sensing, identifiers and internet connectivity. In contrast, CPS emphasizes the consideration of both the cyber and physical aspects, and the providing of integrated systems.

This line of thought is shared by Lee and Seshia [3], as follows: “In our view, the term CPS is more foundational and durable than all of these (author’s note, referring to terms like those in Fig. 1), because it does not directly reference either implementation approaches (e.g. the “Internet” in IoT) nor particular applications (e.g., “Industry” in Industry 4.0). It focuses instead on the fundamental intellectual problem of conjoining the engineering traditions of the cyber and the physical world”.

In this article, we emphasize the etymological meaning of CPS and the resulting characteristics and capabilities of CPS, as a basis for our discussion on implications.

CPS capabilities through synergistic combinations of physical, software and data-driven parts

Törngren and Sellgren provide a characterization of CPS by assessing contrasting differences between physical and software parts/components, in order to discuss characteristics of the key components that literally form part of a CPS [5]. This view is elaborated and extended in Table 1, in particular by adding “data-driven” components. The cyber space, as represented in Table 1 by the “software” and “data-driven” columns, provides unprecedented communication, synchronization, and collaboration opportunities – which may indeed span optimization and orchestration across entire value chains, while encompassing development–operation cycles (data collection, upgrades etc.). Data-driven components incorporate machine learning to provide a new way of programming through learning – with strong dependence on (lots of) quality data. Such components enable unprec-

	Physical components	Software components	Data-driven components
Phenomena and complexity	Multiple coupled physical phenomena, (wear, fatigue, heat, emissions, ..) “slow cycles” and global effects	Pure behavior! State space; bugs; connectivity; variability; Fast local & global effects; “fast cycles”, hidden dependencies	Super-human performance in certain areas; Black-box (deep-learning)
Abstractions, synthesis, and platforms	Approximations, Continuous time & value; No single “platform”, Behavioral model simulation vs. Geometry based synthesis	Digital / discretization “platform” foundations; Logic preserving transformations; Abstracted physical properties	New programming model; model- or learning based. Software under the hood.
Extra-functional properties	Generally established cost and reliability models	Difficult to estimate life-cycle cost; difficult to reason quantitatively about reliability for critical systems	Data quality dependence; Difficult to assess robustness and reliability, Opaqueness; Brittleness

Table 1: Characterization of key CPS “components”, extended from [5]

edented prediction and correspondingly enable proactive behaviours at different time constants.

Further characteristics in Table 1 include “complexity”, highlighting that this in a physical system relates to coupled physical phenomena (with similar orders of magnitude and slow global effects), whereas complexity in the cyber world largely stems from the large state spaces and connectivity, which may cause very rapid global effects. The platforms for these types of components differ. The abstractions made possible in software systems have paved the way for their enormous success – enabling high expressiveness that can be compiled into digital machines. This has however been accomplished by abstracting away physical properties – leading to problems in dealing with, for example, real-time and energy [22].

Combining these components/technologies, to form new integrated CPS components and systems, provides CPS with unique capabilities, to:

- Carry out real-world sensing as well as gathering, storing and processing data and models;
- Provide awareness and prediction through algorithms operating on data and models, concerning both the CPS itself as well as its environment, while taking uncertainty into account;
- Plan and make decisions based on an established awareness and predictions, and given system goals;
- Provide physical structures, acting on these structures (e.g. through force or

torque), and storing, generating and controlling energy;

- Generate physical artefacts (e.g. through additive manufacturing) as well as software/data entities;
- Coordinate the operation of multiple CPS, and collaborate with other CPS and humans!

These capabilities can be applied at different levels (from a component, over a system, to collaborating systems). Consider, for example, a drone used to collect data (in some setting). The drone itself represents a CPS, which could then be used in conjunction with other CPS (say other drones and robots, 3D printers and computing facilities) to provide collaborative capabilities. The described capabilities can also be applied at different time horizons (from real-time to long-term) and at different geographical spans. The combination of cyber and physical is underlined by the concept of digital twins, as a model of a physical item. Connecting physical parts with their corresponding cybermodels provides novel opportunities, such as for detecting failures (needing handling in real-time), predicting maintenance needs and planning for system upgrades.

Many of these proposed capabilities will relate to general definitions of artificial intelligence (AI) in terms of abilities to “think” or “act” like a human being – thus encompassing both cyber (e.g. abstract reasoning and problem solving) and physical (e.g. physical object manipulation) skills [23]. In this context, the capabilities we proposed here are more comprehensive on the physical side, as exemplified with the

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inclusion of generation of physical entities. Similarly, by also emphasizing the physical capabilities, these proposed capabilities augment those identified by autonomic computing systems as shown, for example, by the Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute (so called MAPE-K loop) pattern [24].

It is interesting to reflect on these capabilities and use them to consider the implications of CPS (in the coming sections). It is clear that the envelope and specific performance–cost characteristics of CPS are steadily evolving. Several technological trends are driving improvements in CPS capabilities, for example, through the development of new cost-efficient sensors, not the least driven by the technology push in automated driving and developments in artificial intelligence, and with computational and communication improvements, in particular through the envisioned new tier of edge computing. It is also clear that innovations lie ahead of us that will certainly add entirely new capabilities! An interesting line of investigation would be to

approach the capabilities from the perspective of limitations (e.g. in terms of latency, computations, human machine communication) in order to explore what could be achieved if (or perhaps rather when) these limitations are overcome.

Collaborating CPS (CPSoS) and the missing link – humans!

Communicating and collaborating CPS will increasingly be used to form cyber-physical systems of systems (CPSoS). Collaborating CPS provide special challenges when they lack a single integrator; as a result, multiple organizations and stakeholders need to coordinate and manage the so formed systems of systems (SoS). SoS are often described and characterized in terms of operational and management independence, and by emergent behaviour [14]. A typical example is a traffic system in a city, a situation with a multitude of stakeholders, independent evolution (of streets, vehicles, other infrastructure) and responsibilities that are not always clear. A change in one of the constituent systems may cause

unexpected behaviours (emergence). A typical example of the latter includes the introduction of automated vehicles and the (potential unexpected) effects it may have on the larger traffic system in terms of traffic flows, amount of traffic, accidents etc. The cyber space in terms of connectivity, computing and artificial intelligence is providing new innovation and business opportunities in SoS by enabling data sharing, and by providing new means for coordination and prediction. This in essence means that many new SoS will indeed be CPSoS.

The example CPSoS highlights a number of further challenges and opportunities. For example, what are suitable “rules of the game” for the interactions between a number of CPS (compare autonomous vehicles and in mixed traffic, with vehicles at different levels of automation and humans on the streets)? How can data reasonably be shared and managed and who would be liable in case of an accident? The CPSoS setting further highlights depend-

encies between various CPS including the infrastructure. It is clear that frameworks will be needed in terms of defining goals, policies and mechanisms for interactions among constituent CPS. From the above example and discussion, it should be clear that CPSoS need to be considered as socio-technical systems as their introduction will have large repercussions on a number of societal aspects and stakeholders.

A further very important realization concerns the “missing link” – humans! CPS will not exist in isolation of humans, and will always (as far as we can project) be interrelated with humans who have different roles, including developers, part suppliers, manufacturers, users, operators, and those that maintain CPS. It is apparent that the gap between technological expertise and the understanding of human needs and traits is difficult to bridge, and that the interactions between humans and CPS deserve much more attention. It is of paramount importance that future CPS are developed to be human-centric. This topic will be further elaborated in the section on “Implications and impact of CPS”. Another related concern (also to be followed up in the same section) is that of the increasing complexity of CPS, which requires large teams of experts and companies to collaborate in their development. The net effect of growing CPS complexity is that more entangled aspects need consideration, requiring more knowledge and interactions. Communication between people thus also becomes more and more important along with an understanding of how

our brains work, and how we as humans can collaborate with AI systems [5,27].

CPS opportunities and design space, contributing to a circular economy

The capabilities of CPS lead to a very large potential for innovation and applicability within existing and new domains, including society, farming, healthcare, gaming, industrial production and infrastructure (e.g. water, electricity and transportation). There is of course a difference in how far domains have come. Many domains already have a substantial adoption of CPS, entailing legacy but also efforts to increase connectivity, lifecycle management, automation and smartness. Other domains may have more of a green-field approach, a situation that sometimes could be beneficial (less legacy). See more on the concept of circular economy in the article “Towards circular ICT: from materials to components”.

New CPS applications are driven firmly by the automotive industry (automated vehicles), by telecom (5G and beyond) and by the “internet” giants [21]. Many existing publications describe the strong innovation potential of CPS to create new businesses and for improving many aspects of our lives [1]. The innovation opportunities are representative of a socio-technical shift, with new companies emerging, and some disappearing [11]. The corresponding opportunities provide additional needs and drive innovation in several directions, for example in 3D printing, perception and in computing, providing likely accumulating effects with both technology push and pull.

To illustrate the design space and innovation potential with CPS, consider the Hy-Wire Skateboard concept introduced as early as 2002 by GM (see Figure 2) [25]. With a CPS platform, featuring fuel cells, electrical motors per wheel and a distributed computing platform, this concept demonstrated the possibilities for a substantial vehicle redesign when replacing the mechanical connection (transferring force and position) with a distributed control system (“steer-by-wire”). This also illustrates the concept of “software-defined”, where the properties of the former mechanical steering column are now essentially programmable, limited only by the communication bandwidth, real-time computation, and of the physical constraints imposed by the electrical actuators and power provided. The example moreover highlights some of the inherent challenges and inertia in deploying new CPS; the Hy-wire concepts are not yet on the roads, partly because regulation still does not allow steer by wire, and partly because of the new infrastructure that would be needed for hydrogen-based fuel cells. This dilemma illustrates that innovation opportunities, and barriers for innovation, can be identified at different levels [31].

The CPS capabilities provide new tools that can – and should – be leveraged in order to reduce overall CO₂ emissions and support a circular economy. Taking Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) as a CPSoS example, an ITS can be developed to provide proactive behaviours including the total avoidance of formation of cracks

Figure 2. CPS opportunities illustrated through the Hy-Wire Skateboard concept car (Source: GM, 2002)

and pot-holes in roads, thereby optimizing and reducing efforts, emissions and energy for road repairs, and moreover improving traffic safety. Of course, the potential does not stop here, and extends to energy optimization and traffic efficiency. The example is interesting because it illustrates the opportunity to share data between two separate domains, in this case road infrastructure and road traffic. Combining the data (for example that gathered during road construction, by automated vehicles and infrastructure) with vehicle/infrastructure computational capabilities for learning, prediction, planning and coordination, enables new functionalities and services in the ITS.

In going from the existing “*take-make-dispose*” industrial model, a circular economy represents a paradigm shift in the way of thinking of waste and the lifecycle of materials, components and systems. Perhaps an appropriate way to think about circularity is in terms of “value flows” – where for example “waste” material from production, and components no longer providing adequate performance, are seen as assets instead of as waste. This requires entirely new ways of designing the value chain, highlighting restorative and regenerative abilities to maintain systems and prolong their lifetime, emphasizing reuse, repair, remanufacturing and recycling. There are many ways in which CPS technology can be leveraged to support a circular economy, including by providing:

- Identification and tracing of components and entire products;
- Monitoring and prediction of actual as well as anticipated future states of components/products, in turn facilitating planning and decisions e.g. regarding reuse and repairs;
- Upgrading or downgrading of products to provide an adapted level of services and quality;
- Individualized and tailored production of spare parts.

CPS architecting will be essential for many CPS innovations and for making sure that the added functions are themselves circular. Architecting encompasses well underpinned modularization of both cyber and physical parts, to facilitate all aspects

of reuse, recycling, upgrading, remanufacturing etc. Part of the specific capabilities may be provided through connected edge- and cloud-based services, “augmenting” the CPS. Having these capabilities in place will strongly support service oriented business model for CPS products.

Implications and impact of CPS – towards balanced and managed complexity

As indicated in the previous sections, the many opportunities and market potential of CPS are promoting a strong market penetration in virtually all areas of society. The implications are that CPS will have a corresponding deeper socio-technical impact, where many vital societal systems will be relying on CPS operation to function. It then becomes important to be aware of the risks and complexity of these CPS, and we will therefore turn to elaborate on these.

Just as the capabilities of a CPS draw upon the characteristics of its components, so do, unfortunately, the resulting risks and complexity. A CPS will for example inherit the faults and failure modes of its component technologies with one implication being the characteristic difficulty of understanding fault-propagation and root causes; a system failure may have a multitude of causes. A CPS may for example fail due to triggered software bugs, hardware faults (mechanical, electronic, etc.), environment uncertainties, improper training of machine learning algorithms and security attacks. With increasing levels of automation it is essential to understand that the *automation paradox* remains relevant, and that its importance is increasing; the fact is that higher levels of automation leave humans with even more difficult situations to handle when the automation fails. This is sadly highlighted by the Boeing 737 accidents related to the so-called MCAS system.

CPS will also inherit complexity facets from both the cyber and physical sides, generally implying that CPS can be characterized as hybrid and heterogeneous systems, requiring multiple viewpoints and experts engaged in their development. Similarly a CPS can be said to manifest multiple complexity facets, e.g. related

to its structure, behaviour, heterogeneity, uncertainty and scale [5].

The advancement of CPS capabilities relates naturally to the deployment of CPS in more open and unstructured environments, as is well illustrated by automated vehicles. There will be a widened “cone of uncertainty” when an automated vehicle is deployed and a key question concerns how to assess that the vehicle is ready for the road (homologation). This highlights that current approaches to deal with system safety and security, as well as many other system properties, are challenged [1,17], generally necessitating the connection of developments with operations to improve and adapt CPS during their lifecycle [5]. It is appropriate here to recall the statement of Herbert Simon from his book, *The Sciences of the Artificial* [6]: “The thesis is that certain phenomena are “artificial” in a very specific sense: they are as they are only because of a system’s being moulded, by goals or purposes, to the environment in which it lives.”

When deploying CPS in increasingly complex environments with more advanced CPS goals and capabilities, the corresponding CPS will require a corresponding level of complexity in its realization (e.g. in terms of sensors, algorithms, architecture, etc.). This is the price that has to be paid for the enhanced capabilities.

This increase in complexity poses challenges for us as humans. Our standard way of dealing with complexity is to divide and conquer. While this has worked relatively well so far, the problem with CPS is that, however we divide it, there will be interfaces and dependencies everywhere. CPS are integrated systems with both direct and indirect dependencies between parts [5]. As Sapolsky explains it, humans tend to divide separate aspects into categories – “boxing”. This helps us to focus but is devastating for our ability to “think outside the box” and moreover, these boxes (“viewpoints”), are arbitrary. The human trait of “group thinking”, the fact that we are far from (or have to struggle to be) rational, and the fact that humans are built to take decisions in small groups with local effects, aggravate this problem further [7, 8]. The challenge then

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becomes how we are to deal with increasingly complex CPS. We need not only better techniques to master complexity, but also to get better in avoiding over-complex solutions, moving towards balanced and manageable complexity. So-called featuritis is a well-known problem in software products. As Chris Sacca phrased it: – “Simplicity is hard to build, easy to use and hard to charge for. Complexity is easy to build, hard to use, and easy to charge for” [15].

Referring to the Cynefin framework, many future CPS applications will indeed move us from the “Complicated” to the “Complex” domain – a domain where we lack established theory and methods. It is clear that the shift in complexity corresponds to, and will require, a corresponding paradigm shift in development methodologies and scientific theories. It will moreover, considering the Cynefin framework [33], require that the right strategies are adopted. When moving into the “complex” domain, where appropriate regulations, theories and methodologies are still lacking, there is a need for controlled learning, experimentation, research and technology maturation [11, 29]. A similar concept and realization is that of interactive management [30]. This strongly emphasizes the need for multidisciplinary and multi-stakeholder collaboration. Ideally, societies would want to introduce new CPS in a controlled way, balancing innovation with

some caution. The situation is complicated by the very strong market forces for many CPS applications, platforms and technologies, akin to a modern goldrush. Billions of dollars are being invested in artificial intelligence, IoT and automated vehicle technologies. This brings with it the risk that unnecessarily complex, or otherwise inappropriate, systems may hit the market.

Many further considerations are needed when developing, deploying and even using CPS because of their potential societal-scale implications, including potential side-effects and emergence as described previously. It becomes essential that CPS are designed to be resilient, manageable and understandable, with explicit account for risk management and the system lifecycle. Introducing new or modified CPS/CPSoS, thus requires careful consideration, and supervision and learning during operation; the widened cone of uncertainty implies that unknowns have yet to be unveiled as the systems are used and evolve.

Many CPS will involve gathering data from users in various forms, directly and indirectly. This raises the questions of who owns the data, who can access the data, how this data might be exploited, and to what extent users should care about their privacy. Shoshana Zuboff raises the concerns of “surveillance capitalism”, where (hidden) business models will not only

benefit from exploiting our data, but also control our behaviours [13].

With societal systems relying on CPS, it becomes essential for both organizations, regions and economies to have access to such technologies and the right competence to be able to master them. Along with the CPS socio-technical shift, it is thus essential that education and training are emphasized, there is a need for educational renewal [1,12]. There is a further need to bring awareness to a broader set of stakeholders (including decision makers and the general public) [12]. Efforts are needed for developing new theories and methods to deal with CPS complexity [10,12]. Suitable state-of-the-art approaches to organizational strategies (motivation, incentives, etc.) can lead to superior performance of teams, so called “collective intelligence” [27]. This is an area where awareness needs to be raised. Since CPS complexity is reflected within organizations, it is essential to further research on effective organizations including human-Computer Aided Engineering collaboration to manage the complexity. Managing the paradigm shift requires multi-domain and multidisciplinary collaboration. In this setting, the use of competence networks, i.e. nonprofit collaborations between industry and academia to promote learning and knowledge creation, stands out as a promising approach to deal with the outlined issues [32].

Finally, as we develop highly automated CPS, from individual machines with built-in dynamic risk management, to automated factories and large-scale CPS, ethics becomes an important element in our efforts to create human-centric systems. The built-in risk metrics will relate to the system safety, and how we shape socio-technical systems including CPS with humans, will have a large impact on the quality of people's lives, from working conditions to the roles that humans will have in the future.

Conclusion

In summary, CPS as the integration of computation, networking and physical processes are not new and were already widely available through microprocessor integrated systems in the 1970s and 1980s. The novelty and important aspect of CPS is represented by the new scale of capabilities including integration opportunities across domains and lifecycles, with more open society-scale deployment and a corresponding business model evolution.

Cyber-physical systems with their corresponding trends and facts, provide strong indicators for an ongoing socio-technical shift where we as humans will likely overestimate impact in the short run, but underestimate it in the long run (the so called "Amar's law"). Our societies will involve and rely on collaborating with CPS, and CPS collaborating with humans. We need to balance and manage the complexity and risks of these CPS, and leverage them to deal with the environmental sustainability crisis, showing the way towards a circular economy. To accomplish this we need to stimulate new and true multidisciplinary multi-stakeholder collaborations, promote systems thinking and lifelong learning.

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